

NILRADIKALI BERILGAN BA'ZI YECHILUVCHAN

LEYBNITS ALGEBRALARINING $\frac{1}{2}$ -

DIFFERENSIALLASHLARI

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada nilradikali maksimal uzunlikdagi kvazi-filiform Leybnits algebra bo'lgan yechiluvchan Leybnits algebrasining $\frac{1}{2}$ -differensiallashlari o'rganilgan.

Kalit soz'lar: Leybnits algebra, yechiluvchan Leybnits algebra, nilradikal, algebraning $\frac{1}{2}$ -differensiallashi.

Abstract. In this article we study $\frac{1}{2}$ -derivations of solvable Leibniz algebras whose nilradical is a quasi-filiform Leibniz algebra of maximal length.

Keywords: Leibniz algebra, solvable Leibniz algebra, nilradical, $\frac{1}{2}$ -derivation of algebra

Аннотация. В данной работе изучаются $\frac{1}{2}$ -дифференцирования разрешимых алгебр Лейбница, нильрадикал которых является квази-филиформной алгеброй Лейбница максимальной длины.

Ключевые слова: алгебра Лейбница, разрешимая алгебра Лейбница, нильрадикал, $\frac{1}{2}$ -дифференцирование алгебры.

Ta'rif 1. F maydon ustida aniqlangan L algebraning ixtiyoriy x, y, z elementlari uchun quyidagi Leybnits ayniyati bajarilsa,

$$[x, [y, z]] = [[x, y], z] - [[x, z], y],$$

L algebra Leybnits algebra deyiladi, bu yerda $[-, -]$ – L da aniqlangan ko'paytirish amali.

Ixtiyoriy L Leybnits algebra uchun quyidagi quyi markaziy va hosilaviy ketma-ketliklarni mos ravishda aniqlaymiz:

$$L^1 = L, \quad L^{k+1} = [L^k, L^1]; \quad L^{[1]} = L, \quad L^{[k+1]} = [L^{[k]}, L^{[k]}], \quad k \geq 1.$$

Ta'rif 3. L Leybnits algebra uchun shunday $s \in \mathbb{N}$ son mavjud bo'lib, $L^{[s]} = \mathbf{0}$ (mos ravishda, $L^s = \mathbf{0}$) bo'lsa, u holda L yechiluvchan (mos ravishda, nilpotent) Leybnits algebra deyiladi.

Ta'rif 4. Ixtiyoriy Leybnits algebrasining maksimal nilpotent ideali uning nilradikali deyiladi.

Ta'rif 5. L Leybnits algebra, agar $L^{n-2} \neq 0$ va $L^{n-1} = 0$ bo'lsa kvazi-filiform deyiladi, bu yerda $n = \dim L$.

Nilradikali N va to'ldiruvchi fazosining o'lchami s ga teng bo'lgan barcha yechiluvchan Leybnits algebra lari oilasini $R(N, s)$ bilan belgilaymiz.

Quyidagi teoremda nilradikali maksimal uzunlikdagi kvazi-filiform Leybnits algebra bo'lgan va Q to'ldiruvchi fazosining o'lchami ikkiga teng bo'lgan yechiluvchan Leybnits algebra larini tasnifi keltiriladi.

Teorema 1. [2] $R(M^{1,0}, 2)$ algebra lar oilasining ixtiyoriy algebra si quyidagi algebra ga izomorf:

$$R(M^{1,0}, 2): \begin{cases} [e_1, e_1] = e_n, & [e_i, e_1] = e_{i+1}, & 2 \leq i \leq n-2, \\ [e_1, x_1] = e_1, & [e_i, x_1] = (i-2)e_i, & 3 \leq i \leq n-1, \\ [e_n, x_1] = 2e_n, & [x_1, e_1] = -e_1, \\ [e_i, x_2] = e_i, & & 2 \leq i \leq n-1. \end{cases}$$

Teorema 2. [2] $R(M^{2,\lambda}, 2)$ algebra lar oilasining ixtiyoriy algebra si quyidagi algebra lardan biriga izomorf;

$$R(M^{2,0}, 2): \begin{cases} [e_i, e_1] = e_{i+1}, & 1 \leq i \leq n-3, & [e_{n-1}, e_1] = e_n, \\ [e_i, x_1] = ie_i, & 1 \leq i \leq n-2, & [e_n, x_1] = e_n, \\ [x_1, e_1] = -e_1, & [e_{n-1}, x_2] = e_{n-1}, & [e_n, x_2] = e_n. \end{cases}$$

$$R(M^{2,-1}, 2): \begin{cases} [e_i, e_1] = e_{i+1}, & 1 \leq i \leq n-3, & [x_1, e_1] = -e_1, \\ [e_{n-1}, e_1] = -[e_1, e_{n-1}] = e_n, & [e_n, x_1] = -[x_1, e_n] = e_n, \\ [e_i, x_1] = ie_i, & 1 \leq i \leq n-2, \\ [e_{n-1}, x_2] = -[x_2, e_{n-1}] = e_{n-1}, & [e_n, x_2] = -[x_2, e_n] = e_n. \end{cases}$$

Ta'rif 4. Aytaylik d - L Leybnits algebra sining chiziqli almashtirishi bo'lsin. Agar ixtiyoriy $x, y \in L$ lar uchun quyidagi tenglik bajarilsa

$$d([x, y]) = \frac{1}{2} ([d(x), y] + [x, d(y)]),$$

u holda d chiziqli almashtirishga L Leybnits algebra sining $\frac{1}{2}$ -differensiallashi deyiladi.

[1] ishda $R(M^{1,0}, 2)$, $R(M^{2,0}, 2)$ va $R(M^{2,-1}, 2)$ algebra larining differensiallashlari topilgan. Quyidagi tasdiqda $R(M^{1,0}, 2)$ algebra ni $\frac{1}{2}$ -differensiallashi topilgan.

Tasdiq 1. $R(M^{1,0}, 2)$ algebra ning ixtiyoriy $\frac{1}{2}$ -differensiallashi quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi:

$$d(e_i) = a_{1,i}e_i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n,$$

$$d(x_i) = a_{1,i}x_i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq 2.$$

Isbot. Aytaylik $d - R(M^{1,0}, 2)$ algebraning $\frac{1}{2}$ -differensiallashi bo'lsin. $d - \frac{1}{2}$ -differensiallashni hosil qiluvchi bazis elementlari uchun berish yetarli, shuning uchun aytaylik,

$$d(e_1) = \sum_{i=1}^n a_{1,i}e_i + a_{1,n+1}x_1 + a_{1,n+2}x_2,$$

$$d(e_2) = \sum_{i=1}^n a_{2,i}e_i + a_{2,n+1}x_1 + a_{2,n+2}x_2,$$

$$d(x_1) = \sum_{i=1}^n b_{1,i}e_i + b_{1,n+1}x_1 + b_{1,n+2}x_2,$$

$$d(x_2) = \sum_{i=1}^n b_{2,i}e_i + b_{2,n+1}x_1 + b_{2,n+2}x_2$$

bo'lsin.

$\frac{1}{2}$ -differensiallashni ta'rifidan foydalanib quyidagi tengliklarni qarab chiqamiz.

$$1. \quad d([e_1, e_2]) = \frac{1}{2}[d(e_1), e_2] + \frac{1}{2}[e_1, d(e_2)] \quad \text{tenglikni qarab bundan esa,}$$

$a_{2,1} = 0, a_{2,n+1} = 0$ natijalarni olamiz.

Bu natijalar orqali

$$d(e_2) = \sum_{i=2}^n a_{2,i}e_i + a_{2,n+2}x_2$$

kabi ko'rinishiga erishamiz.

$$2. \quad d([e_1, x_2]) = \frac{1}{2}[d(e_1), x_2] + \frac{1}{2}[e_1, d(x_2)] \quad \text{ni qaraylik. } d([e_1, x_2]) = 0 \text{ ga teng.}$$

Bundan quyidagicha natija olamiz:

$$b_{2,1} = 0, b_{2,n+1} = 0, a_{1,i} = 0, \quad 2 \leq i \leq n - 2.$$

Bundan

$$d(e_1) = a_{1,1}e_1 + a_{1,n}e_n + a_{1,n+1}x_1 + a_{1,n+2}x_2, \quad (1)$$

$$d(x_2) = \sum_{i=2}^n b_{2,i}e_i + b_{2,n+2}x_2$$

natijalarni olamiz.

$$3. \quad \text{Endi } d([e_1, e_1]) = \frac{1}{2}[d(e_1), e_1] + \frac{1}{2}[e_1, d(e_1)] \text{ tenglikni ko'raylik.}$$

$d([e_1, e_1]) = d(e_n)$ bo'ladi.

Bundan

$$d(e_n) = a_{1,1}e_n \quad (2)$$

olamiz.

$$4. d([e_2, x_1]) = \frac{1}{2}[d(e_2), x_1] + \frac{1}{2}[e_2, d(x_1)] \text{ ni qaraymiz}$$

Bu tenglikdan

$$a_{2,i} = 0, \quad 4 \leq i \leq n-2,$$

$$b_{1,n+2} = 0,$$

$$b_{1,1} = -a_{2,3}$$

natijalarni olamiz.

Olingan natijalar orqali kerakli tengliklarni topamiz.

$$d(e_2) = a_{2,2}e_2 + a_{2,3}e_3 + a_{2,n+2}x_2, \quad (3)$$

$$d(x_1) = -a_{2,3}e_1 + \sum_{i=2}^n b_{1,i}e_i + b_{1,n+1}x_1$$

$$5. \text{ Endi } d([x_1, e_1]) = \frac{1}{2}[d(x_1), e_1] + \frac{1}{2}[x_1, d(e_1)] \text{ tenglikni qaraylik.}$$

Olgan tengligimizni (1) ga tenglaymiz va quyidagi natijalarni olamiz:

$$b_{1,n+1} = a_{1,1},$$

$$a_{2,3} = 2a_{1,n}, \quad (1')$$

$$b_{1,i} = 0, \quad 2 \leq i \leq n-2,$$

$$a_{1,n+1} = 0, \quad a_{1,n+2} = 0.$$

Olingan natijalardan quyidagilarga ega bo'lamiz:

$$d(e_1) = a_{1,1}e_1 + a_{1,n}e_n, \quad (4)$$

$$d(x_1) = -2a_{1,n}e_1 + b_{1,n-1}e_{n-1} + b_{1,n}e_n + a_{1,1}x_1. \quad (5)$$

$$6. d([e_2, x_2]) = \frac{1}{2}[d(e_2), x_2] + \frac{1}{2}[e_2, d(x_2)] \text{ tenglikni olaylik.}$$

Yuqoridan $a_{2,2} = b_{2,n+2}$, $a_{2,3} = b_{2,2}$, $a_{2,n+2} = 0$ ni olamiz. Bundan

$$d(e_2) = a_{2,2}e_2 + a_{2,3}e_3$$

ni hosil qilamiz.

$$7. d([e_n, x_1]) = \frac{1}{2}[d(e_n), x_1] + \frac{1}{2}[e_n, d(x_1)] =$$

$$\frac{1}{2}[d(e_n), x_1] + \frac{1}{2}[e_n, d(x_1)] = (a_{1,1} + b_{1,n+1})e_n$$

ni olamiz. Ko'rish qiyin emaski $d(e_n) = \frac{1}{2}(a_{1,1} + b_{1,n+1})e_n$ bo'ladi.

Olganimizni (2) bilan tenglaymiz va

$$a_{1,1} = b_{1,n+1} \quad (2')$$

ni olamiz.

$$8. d([x_1, x_2]) = \frac{1}{2}[d(x_1), x_2] + \frac{1}{2}[x_1, d(x_2)] \text{ tenglikdan quyidagi natijani olamiz:}$$

$$b_{1,n-1} = 0.$$

Natijani va (1') ni (5) ga olib borib qo'ysak $d(x_1) = -a_{2,3}e_1 + b_{1,n}e_n + b_{1,n+1}x_1$ hosil bo'ladi.

$$9. d([e_1, x_1]) = \frac{1}{2}[d(e_1), x_1] + \frac{1}{2}[e_1, d(x_1)] \text{ ifodani olaylik. } d([e_1, x_1]) = d(e_1)$$

hosil bo'ladi. Bu tenglikdan $d(e_1) = \frac{1}{2}(a_{1,1} + b_{1,n+1} - a_{2,3})e_1 + \frac{1}{2}a_{1,n}e_n$ natijani olamiz.

Olingan tenglikni (4) ga tenglaymiz va

$$a_{1,n} = 0, a_{1,1} = b_{1,n+1} - a_{2,3} \quad (3')$$

tengliklarni olamiz. (2') ni (3') ga qo'ysak,

$$a_{2,3} = 0 \quad (4')$$

natijani olamiz. Olingan natijalarni tengliklarga qo'ysak

$$d(x_1) = a_{1,1}x_1 + b_{1,n}e_n, \quad d(e_1) = a_{1,1}e_1, \quad d(e_2) = a_{2,2}e_2$$

larga ega bo'lamiz.

10. $\frac{1}{2}$ - differensiallashni $[x_2, e_1]$ ko'paytma uchun qarasak,

$$d([x_2, e_1]) = \frac{1}{2}[d(x_2), e_1] + \frac{1}{2}[x_2, d(e_1)]. \text{ Bundan}$$

$$b_{2,i} = 0, \quad 2 \leq i \leq n-2$$

kelib chiqadi. Buni o'rniga olib borib qo'ysak

$$d(x_2) = b_{2,n-1}e_{n-1} + b_{2,n}e_n + a_{2,2}x_2 \quad (6)$$

ni hosil qilamiz.

$$11. d([x_2, x_1]) = \frac{1}{2}[d(x_2), x_1] + \frac{1}{2}[x_2, d(x_1)] \text{ tenglikdan}$$

$$0 = \frac{1}{2}[d(x_2), x_1] + \frac{1}{2}[x_2, d(x_1)] = 2b_{2,n}e_n + (n-3)b_{2,n-1}e_{n-1} \text{ ni topamiz. Bundan}$$

$b_{2,n} = 0, b_{2,n-1} = 0$ olamiz. Olinganlarni (6) ga olib borib qo'ysak

$$d(x_2) = a_{2,2}x_2$$

tenglikka ega bo'lamiz.

$$12. d([x_1, x_1]) = \frac{1}{2}[d(x_1), x_1] + \frac{1}{2}[x_1, d(x_1)] \text{ tenglikni qarasak,}$$

$$0 = \frac{1}{2}[d(x_1), x_1] + \frac{1}{2}[x_1, d(x_1)] = 2b_{1,n}e_n \text{ bo'ladi. Bu yerdan } b_{1,n} = 0 \text{ ni olamiz. Olingan}$$

natijalarni olib tengliklarga qo'ysak

$$d(x_1) = a_{1,1}x_1$$

natijani hosil qilamiz.

$$13. d([e_2, e_1]) = \frac{1}{2}[d(e_2), e_1] + \frac{1}{2}[e_2, d(e_1)] \text{ tenglikdan } d(e_3) = \frac{1}{2}(a_{1,1} + a_{2,2})e_3$$

tenglikni olamiz. Bundan $d(e_3) = \frac{1}{4}((a_{1,1} + 3a_{2,2})e_3)$ tenglikni olamiz. Yuqorida olingan bu tengliklardan

$$a_{2,2} = a_{1,1} \quad (7)$$

ekanligini olamiz. Bundan $d(e_2) = a_{1,1}e_2$, $d(e_3) = a_{1,1}e_3$, $d(x_2) = a_{1,1}x_2$ bo'ladi.

$$14. \frac{1}{2} - \text{differensialni } d([e_3, e_1]) = \frac{1}{2}[d(e_3), e_1] + \frac{1}{2}[e_3, d(e_1)] \text{ tenglikdan}$$

$d(e_4) = a_{1,1}e_4$ ga ega bo'lamiz. $d(e_5)$ ni hisoblab, olingan natijalarni umumlashtiramiz.

$$15. d([e_4, e_1]) = \frac{1}{2}[d(e_4), e_1] + \frac{1}{2}[e_4, d(e_1)] \text{ ni qaraylik, bundan}$$

$$d(e_5) = a_{1,1}e_5$$

natijani olamiz.

Olingan natijalarni umumlashtirib, matematik induksiya yordamida

$$d(e_i) = a_{1,1}e_i, \quad 3 \leq i \leq n-1,$$

tenglikni osonlik bilan olishimiz mumkin. Shunday qilib,

$$d(e_i) = a_{1,1}e_i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n,$$

$$d(x_i) = a_{1,1}x_i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq 2.$$

$\frac{1}{2}$ - differensiallashni qolgan barcha ko'paytmalar uchun qarasaq, faqat ayniyatlarni olamiz. □

Teorema. $R(M^{2,0}, 2)$ algebraning ixtiyoriy $\frac{1}{2}$ -differensiallashi quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi:

$$d(e_i) = a_{1,1}e_i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n,$$

$$d(x_i) = a_{1,1}x_i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq 2.$$

$R(M^{2,-1}, 2)$ algebraning ixtiyoriy $\frac{1}{2}$ -differensiallashi quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi:

$$d(e_i) = a_{1,1}e_i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n,$$

$$d(x_1) = b_{1,n}e_n + a_{1,1}x_1,$$

$$d(x_2) = b_{1,n}e_n + a_{1,1}x_2.$$

Isbot. $R(M^{1,0}, 2)$ algebraning yuqorida keltirilgan isbotiga o'xshash isbotlanadi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

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